

SCLEROTHERAPY FOR VARICOSE AND SPIDER VEINS

A medical procedure that is used to eliminate varicose veins and spider veins are Sclerotherapy. this [vein treatment](#) involves a solution that is being injected into the vein directly. This solution will cause collapsing and sticking of veins that results in the irritation of blood vessels. This vessel then turns into scar tissue over time. It is being in use since the 1930s and is a proven procedure.

Eligibility for Sclerotherapy

You have to consult a **vein doctor** prior to sclerotherapy, who decides if you are eligible for a procedure or not. If you are pregnant, then you are not eligible for sclerotherapy. If you are taking birth control pills then you are eligible for sclerotherapy. Your eligibility will decide on an individual basis if you have a blood clot in the past. It will depend on the overall health area for **vein treatments** as well as for the clot.

Process of Sclerotherapy

A salt solution is being injected into the veins through a needle in most cases of sclerotherapy. In this type of **varicose vein treatment**, you may experience cramping and

mild discomfort for two to three minutes in case of larger veins. This procedure requires 20 to 30 minutes only. The general medical condition of a patient also plays an important role in injecting the veins. In one injecting session, the number of veins depends on the location and size of the veins. After the procedure, you should not have to do any kind of activity for a few days. It is performed by a **vein specialist** and can be performed in a doctor's office.

Before sclerotherapy

You have to avoid any kind of medication before having sclerotherapy. If you are taking any kind of medicine then you should talk to your doctor about that. You are not permitted to apply any lotion on your legs just before sclerotherapy and if you need to take an antibiotic then you should consult with your doctor.

Some **vein doctor near me** will advise you to avoid anti-inflammatory drugs or medication for 48-72 hours before the sclerotherapy. A medicine named Tylenol does not affect this procedure.

Side effects of Sclerotherapy

After sclerotherapy, it is possible that you may receive certain side effects. You can feel itching, redness, and pain in that particular area in which solution is injected during the procedure of sclerotherapy.

The larger veins required several weeks and months to become lumpy and hard after being injected in this procedure.

After having [spider vein treatment](#), brown spots or lines may appear at the vein site. They disappear within three months in most cases.

After sclerotherapy

You will be able to do your regular activity after having the procedure of sclerotherapy. Walking will be highly encouraged after sclerotherapy. You will be advised to wear compression stockings in order to provide support to treated veins of the legs. Your **vein specialist** will recommend some other exercises and precautions to you after the procedure of sclerotherapy.